

ESTABLISHMENT OF LEGAL BASIS OF HOLY STEPS AND PILGRIMAGES IN THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

Sattorova I.G

Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

Uzbek language and literature, teacher of the department of social sciences, chairman of the women's advisory council of the institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331762>

Abstract: *In this article, the large-scale reforms carried out in the field of tourism in recent years, the decrees and decisions adopted in this regard, and their implementation issues, as well as historical sites, their preservation, respectful treatment, and safe delivery to the next generation, scientific opinions -theoretical views and suggestions are mentioned.*

Key words: *Tourism, cultural heritage, shrine, pilgrimage tourism.*

After the Republic of Uzbekistan gained its independence, much attention was paid to the improvement of holy places and shrines, as well as to the creation of their legal bases, as in all other fields. Our country is a country with great potential in the field of tourism, the Uzbek people have a rich historical and cultural heritage. Today, our country is known for its world-famous

Islamic shrines. Therefore, the number of tourists visiting our country for the purpose of pilgrimage tourism is increasing year by year.

Uzbekistan has always been a center of intersection of many cultures and civilizations, where various religions have been propagated, therefore unique monuments related to Islam, Buddhism and Christianity have been preserved.

Along with ancient monuments, sacred shrines, historical and cultural monuments, the efforts made in this direction in our country, which attracts tourists with its unique culture and traditions, beautiful nature and beautiful corners, are gaining importance in the further development of the tourism industry and infrastructure.

About two million tourists from 70 countries of the world visit our country every year. For them, cultural-historical tourism remains the most popular. In addition, more than 110 of the existing 500 tourism companies are consistently operating in international destinations, which is an important factor in attracting tourists to our country.

We can clearly see this in the case of the research conducted by the World Travel and Tourism Council (WTTC) on "Economic results of the travel and tourism industry", where our republic is listed as one of the five countries where the tourism sector is rapidly developing.

Our country is one of the countries that ratified the Convention on the Protection of the Universal Cultural and Natural Heritage. This Convention was adopted by the UN UNESCO organization on November 16, 1972 in Paris, and its main goal is to preserve the historical monuments of

the whole world in their original state and pass them on to future generations. The Convention consists of 8 sections and 38 articles.

In order to implement this convention and adapt its norms to our national legislation, the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Law "On the Protection and Use of Cultural Heritage Objects" on August 30, 2001. The law is structurally composed of 8 sections and 36 articles. Law "On the protection and use of cultural heritage objects". T. 2001).

In order to implement the convention and the law, a number of remarkable works have been carried out in our Republic, in particular in the Samarkand region. In particular, the master plan of historical architectural values of Samarkand was developed. On July 29, 2020, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the protection of cultural heritage objects and further improvement of their use" was adopted. During the preparation and implementation period, historical monuments and architectural monuments belonging to those times were not renovated, but many wonderful modern architectural complexes, imbued with national traditions: Imam al-Bukhari in Samarkand region, Imam al-Motru di in Samarkand, Ahmad al-

Farghani in Kuva, Burkhaniddi in Margilon. al-Marginani mausoleums, "Mourning Mother", "Memorial of Martyrs" complexes in Tashkent, Sahibqiron Amir Temur in Tashkent, Samarkand, Shahrisabz cities, Mirzo Ulug'bek, Alisher Navoi in Tashkent, Alpomish in Termiz, Jalaluddin Manguberdi statues in Urganch, sculptural compositions were built that enriched our cultural heritage. . Uzbekistan - art, science? It is an important and cultural center of the brightest achievements in the fields of architecture, the richest foundation of historical memory that plays an important role in shaping the modern spiritual and cultural landscape of the nation. Restoration of Islamic values and preservation of Islamic architectural monuments are of particular importance in the spiritual development of the nation.

At the beginning of 1990, with the independence of Uzbekistan, the restoration of the values and traditions of the Islamic religion began. On June 2, 1990, the Decree "On the Pilgrimage of Muslims to Saudi Arabia" was adopted and many of our Muslims had the opportunity to go on the pilgrimage.

Article 49 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan

"Citizens are obliged to carefully preserve the historical, spiritual and cultural heritage of the people of Uzbekistan.

The clause "Cultural monuments are under state protection" (Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T. "Uzbekistan" 2019. p. 17) was deleted.

During the years of independence, a number of legal regulations were adopted

done In particular, there were 12 Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 8 Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 13 Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 21 Decrees of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The path of restoration of national values, history, and traditions chosen from the first days of our independence made a great contribution to the spiritual environment of the society, the formation of positive historical thinking in it, and especially to the education of the culture of historical memory in the minds of the representatives of the modern generation. Thanks to the participation of the general population in the good work of restoring the holy places and shrines in all regions of our country, a huge program in this regard was successfully implemented.

According to Article 64 of the Code of Administrative Responsibility

of the Republic of Uzbekistan entitled "Violation of the rules for the protection and use of historical and cultural monuments", intentional violation of these rules may result in a fine of one to three times the minimum wage or Article 32 of the Criminal Code According to the law, if it is committed after the application of administrative punishment for such actions, the intentional destruction of historical or cultural monuments that are under state protection, a fine of up to fifty times the minimum wage, or correctional labor for up to three years, or deprivation of liberty for up to six months. Punishment is indicated. It is also noted that if the same actions cause a large amount of damage, they will be punished with a fine in the amount of fifty to one hundred times the minimum monthly salary or imprisonment for up to three years. (Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent Justice, 1995. Issue 9, p. 25.)

Today, pilgrimage tourism is a priority direction of state policy. Recently, that is, according to the Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on April 6, 2021, "On measures to further improve the state management system in the fields of tourism, sports and cultural heritage", the Ministry of Tourism and Sports on the basis of the Ministry of

Physical Education and Sports and the State Committee for Tourism Development and the departments of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and Tashkent city, district (city) departments of the Ministry were established.

On May 27, 2020, the President of our Republic Shavkat Mirziyoyev will get acquainted with the presentation of projects in the fields of tourism and privatization of state assets. In it, "In today's era of globalization, countries and people are inextricably linked. Any country in the world is just a step away. Therefore, tourism has become one of the biggest industries. Experts call tourism "inexhaustible oil". The economy of some countries is completely built on the tourism industry. According to the analysis, people travel the most to countries with a flight time of up to 5 hours. There are about 60 countries and 3 billion people around our country. This means a huge tourism market. But this opportunity was not used for many years. Due to the lack of favorable economic and organizational-legal conditions, everyone was working in their own way.

In accordance with the Decree of the head of our state dated December 2, 2016 "On measures to ensure rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of

Uzbekistan", tourism was designated as a strategic branch of our country's economy. Citizens of a number of countries have been allowed to stay in our country without a visa for up to 30 days, the procedure for issuing visas to many more has been simplified, the visa-free regime has been introduced for citizens of about 90 countries, which attracts tourists even more. Therefore, in 2017, almost 2,700,000 tourists visited Uzbekistan, and in 2019, this figure reached 6.7 million. In 2020, Uzbekistan was recognized as the most attractive tourist destination in more than ten prestigious international publications.

Due to the Decision of February 7, 2018 "On measures to ensure rapid development of domestic tourism", domestic tourism is also expanding.

The coronavirus pandemic has also had a major impact on the tourism industry. Therefore, on May 28, 2020, the Decree "On urgent measures to support the tourism sector to reduce the negative impact of the corona virus pandemic" was issued.

On June 19, 2020, the Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to develop the tourism industry in strict compliance with the enhanced regime of sanitary and epidemiological safety" was adopted. (Khalk Sozi newspaper

June 23, 2020)

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020, "We will continue consistent reforms in the development of tourism in 2021. Special attention is paid to the development of pilgrimage tourism and domestic tourism. "Also, 1 trillion soums will be allocated from the budget for the improvement of land areas, water and road infrastructures around tourism facilities," they said. During his visit to Samarkand region in July 2019, the Honorable President noted the need to expand the Imam Bukhari complex, "... this place should be worthy of the knowledge and status of our grandfather Imam Bukhari in the Islamic world. This is the basis of pilgrimage tourism in our country. No matter how many pilgrims come to this place, there should be comfortable conditions.

By the way, today the development of pilgrimage tourism is a priority direction of state policy. Improvement works of holy places and shrines were further strengthened.

But in order to develop pilgrimage tourism on a large scale, a number of things must be done: increase the number of hotels, lower the price of the existing ones, train guides who have a deep

knowledge of this field, and improve the sanitary-hygiene conditions of the toilets around the pilgrimage sites.

REFERENCES:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси. Т."Ўзбекистон" 2019.17-бет.
2. Маданий мерос объектларини муҳофаза қилиш ва улардан фойдаланиш тўғрисида»ги Қонун.Т.2001.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Маъмурий жавобгарлик тўғрисидаги кодекс. Тошкент Адолат, 1995. 9-сон.25-бет.)
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президенти Шавкат Мирзиёевнинг Олий Мажлисга Мурожаатномаси. Халқ сўзи газетаси 2020 йил 31- декабрь.
5. Туризм соҳасини санитария-эпидемиологик хавфсизлигининг кучайтирилган режими талабаларига қатъий риоя қилган ҳолда ривожлантиришга доир чоратадбирлар тўғрисида" Қарори қабул қилинди. Халқ сўзи газетаси 2020-йил 23-июнь.

JOURNAL OF PUBLIC PEDAGOGIES

ISSN 2207-4422

IMPAKT FAKTOR: 7.455

